

From Potsdam to London and Back: What Happens When Plagiarism Investigations Derail

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Abstract: This article examines how King’s College London and the University of Potsdam have handled plagiarism allegations against Walter Homolka as a case study in the governance of academic integrity in cross-national higher education systems. Drawing on scholarship that conceptualizes scientific misconduct as a systemic rather than purely individual phenomenon, the analysis focuses on delays, restricted transparency, and inconsistencies in communication and access to information. Three governance issues are highlighted: the prolonged lack of procedural clarity surrounding King’s College London’s internal review; vulnerabilities in the University of Potsdam’s application of its own plagiarism policy and freedom-of-information regulations; and the distinctive risks these weaknesses pose for the credibility of a newly institutionalized academic field—Jewish Theology. The article does not adjudicate the underlying allegations. Instead, it argues that the case exposes structural deficiencies in how universities manage serious accusations of academic misconduct, and that these deficiencies point to a need for clearer procedures, more consistent communication, and strengthened institutional safeguards, in full recognition of the intricate dynamics of “regulative power”.

Keywords: academic integrity; plagiarism investigations; scientific misconduct; university governance; public knowledge; transparency and accountability; freedom of information; institutional ethics; knowledge systems; vulnerable academic fields.

I am not aware of any case study from confessional theology (the discipline of denomination-specific academic theology) in the research-integrity literature. This paper helps to fill that gap by advancing the thesis that, in the specific context of the plagiarism allegations concerning Rabbi Professor Walter Homolka, Ph.D., Ph.D., the universities involved did not adequately deploy the instruments at their disposal to fulfil their academic responsibility to uphold minimal standards of accountability and integrity within the social system of public knowledge they are mandated to serve. I argue that this shortfall not only raises legal questions but is also ethically significant, as it carries the risk of harming the reputation of the accused, the scholar whose work may have been plagiarized, those who advance the allegations on the basis of publicly available evidence, the academic integrity of a developing discipline, and ultimately the system of public knowledge that academic institutions are meant to support.

This thesis is offered as an institutional analysis and not as a judgement on individual conduct. This paper does not assess, confirm, or deny the validity of the plagiarism allegations, but examines solely how the universities involved have handled them. The Homolka case is treated here solely as a case study in institutional response to allegations of misconduct, with the aim of drawing general lessons for research-integrity governance. The paper proceeds in the spirit of Broad and Wade’s (1985, 141) insight that the study of scientific fraud illuminates the ways in which non-rational elements operate within scientific processes and thereby reveals that science “is both logical and illogical, rational and irrational, open-minded and dogmatic.” In this sense, plagiarism is of particular interest to historians, philosophers and sociologists of science, as well as to policy makers.

The case under consideration concerns confessional theology, which permits in unique ways to explore the interaction of the logical and illogical, rational and irrational, open-minded and dogmatic in the context of science. It is no longer self-evident in what sense theology can be regarded as a science, although the matter is much more complicated than it may seem at first

sight (see, e.g., Göcke 2018, 2020; Murphy 1990; Swinburne 2007). Once celebrated as the “queen of the sciences,” theology has, in many institutional contexts, suffered a substantial loss of standing as a serious academic discipline, even in Germany with its longstanding tradition of fully integrating confessional theology into its public university system (see, e.g., Heckel 1986, 1987). Germany is rather unique in Europe (see Brink 2020) in that it not only continues to maintain confessional theology within its public universities (see, e.g. Krötke 1994; Howard 2006), but has in fact decided to expand its presence there (see, e.g., Agai 2015, 2024; Wissenschaftsrat 2010), despite the trend toward accelerated secularization at the population level. In effect, in addition to its conceptual contribution to understanding institutional responses to alleged misconduct in a very specific case, the paper brings into view a largely neglected sector in the research-integrity literature—confessional theology in a public university system—and thus helps to broaden the disciplinary range of case studies in the relevant field to inform policy assessments of the interaction of the logical and illogical, rational and irrational, open-minded and dogmatic in the context of science from a rather unique angle.

Philip Kitcher (2011, 85) argues that the “forms of inquiry designated as ‘sciences’, where the term is used inclusively to cover studies of art, literature and music, investigations of human behavior, culture and societies, as well as facets of the physical and organic world, play a central role” in systems of public knowledge, which he defines as “that body of shared information on which people draw in pursuing their own projects.” Kitcher (2011, 91) identifies four types of foundational value judgements that undergird any system of public knowledge: (1) what research questions are worth pursuing; (2) who is authorized to make submissions to the public repository of knowledge; (3) how such submissions are to be certified; and (4) how certified knowledge is to be disseminated. These normative decisions shape the institutional authority of science and condition whether disciplines—such as confessional theology—can acquire scientific legitimacy. No practice is intrinsically scientific, and the value judgments that underpin a society’s definition of science are not merely epistemic, i.e., concerning the nature of knowledge in a narrow sense of true beliefs, but necessarily also political, cultural, moral, and at times even religious (see Douglas 2021).

With these philosophical clarifications in place, the case at hand offers an illuminating window into the position of “Jewish Theology” in Germany’s system of public knowledge, because Homolka is professor at the University of Potsdam’s rather unique “School of Jewish Theology”—an institute by constitution, with powers comparable to that of a faculty, and fully integrated in the university. Potsdam is the only place in Europe that trains future rabbis and cantors in the Jewish traditions of the “reform” and “conservative” movements. The establishment of the School contributed to raising the national and international profile of the University of Potsdam, and the university benefited from this enhanced visibility until 2022. The School’s institutional set-up required carefully calibrated cooperation among religious, state, and university actors. In 2022, the arrangement that had been in place since 2013 collapsed, and it remains unclear what the future holds for the School.

Universities occupy a pivotal position in systems of public knowledge because they are both executors of educational state policy and agents in the normative discourse about the very nature of the system. This is true even for Germany’s public universities, despite their formal embeddedness in a state-regulated framework of higher education. In this sense then, I am going

to look into the actions of two universities tasked with investigating the plagiarism allegations under consideration.

Here is the roadmap for what follows. First, I outline the plagiarism allegations against Homolka as registered by the University of Potsdam in 2022 and partly referred to King's College London (1). Second, I summarize my attempts to obtain clarity as to why, more than three years later, the matter remains unresolved (2). Third, I offer an analysis of the situation, focusing both on the nature and institutional implications of the allegations and on the responses of the universities involved (3). In this context, I will offer policy recommendations.

(1) The Allegations

The summary that follows is provided solely to contextualize the institutional responses at issue and is not intended to assess the merits of the allegations. As I will argue, however, the seriousness and specificity of these allegations demand an institutional response consistent with the transparency, timeliness, and procedural clarity that existing higher-education policy frameworks would lead one to expect. Plagiarism is a form of appropriation: it takes someone else's intellectual labour and passes it off as one's own. Because authorship and originality function as currencies within academic systems—shaping hiring, promotion, funding allocation, and professional reputation—plagiarism redistributes academic goods in ways that undermine both fairness and trust in institutional processes.

Beyond questions of credit, plagiarism disrupts the reliability of the scholarly record, obscuring the origins of ideas and complicating the attribution of responsibility, expertise, and debate. It may conceal limitations acknowledged in the original work, and it destabilizes citation networks that are essential for cumulative inquiry. At a more structural level, plagiarism investigations are not fundamentally about footnotes but about the governance of knowledge: they touch on justice, institutional credibility, and the capacity of academic organisations to regulate themselves. Academic staff are not merely private individuals; they function as role models and as agents of institutional legitimacy. When a system appears to tolerate plagiarism at senior levels, it signals to students and early-career researchers that ethical shortcuts are acceptable and erodes confidence in the mechanisms designed to uphold research integrity.

These dynamics become even more consequential in fields whose institutional position is still being consolidated. Jewish Theology in Potsdam represents a salient example. As a relatively recent addition to Germany's public-university landscape—anchored in an unusual configuration of state authority, community representation, and academic evaluation—its legitimacy depends heavily on the perception that its governance structures operate in accordance with the same integrity norms that guide more established disciplines. When allegations remain unresolved for extended periods or when the rationales for institutional inaction are not communicated transparently, the uncertainty generated is not merely procedural. It affects the discipline's standing within the broader system of public knowledge by raising questions about whether it is integrated into the standard accountability architecture or functions under exceptional conditions. In this way, delayed or opaque investigations have system-level consequences: they shape the perceived credibility, autonomy, and institutional maturity of the field itself.

Legal and policy frameworks exist precisely to prevent such erosion. If authorship is understood as a normative claim protected by academic governance, institutions have a duty to assess credible allegations with due process and clarity. Prompt investigation is essential not only to ensure equitable distribution of academic rewards but also to preserve stable expectations of accountability, both internally and externally. In younger disciplines whose position within national higher-education systems is still emerging, these duties carry particular significance: they safeguard the field's capacity to develop under conditions of institutional trust rather than under the shadow of unresolved procedural uncertainty.

On 27 September 2022, a report was published that had been commissioned by the president of the University of Potsdam (The Report 2022 hereafter). The Report (2022, p. 1) offers as reasons for its existence that in January 2022, a colleague of Homolka's at the "School of Jewish Theology" submitted serious allegations of misconduct against Homolka. On 11 January 2022 a letter of that colleague outlining those allegations was sent to the university administration, and later to the Ministry of Science, Research, and Culture of the State of Brandenburg (MWFK) on 31 January 2022. In a letter dated 17 February 2022, the MWFK informed the President of the University of Potsdam that responsibility for reviewing the allegations contained in the letter lies with the University President. The Ministry therefore requested that the University assume responsibility for examining the allegations.

As a result, in March 2022, an investigative commission was established, according to The Report (2022), whose members were the university's central gender equality officer, as chair; the Vice President for Research, Early-Career Scholars, and Equal Opportunity, as deputy chair; the university's Senate ombudsperson; the head of the university's human resources and legal affairs division; and the chair of the University of Potsdam's Committee for the Investigation of Scientific Misconduct. The allegations of misconduct in connection with Homolka's scholarly publications were part of the investigation by the commission. Several of Professor Homolka's scholarly publications were made available to the commission. A hearing with Professor Homolka and his partner was held on 22 July 2022, supplemented by email correspondence that took place after the hearing.

The Report (2022, pp. 13-14) addresses the allegations of academic misconduct against Homolka as follows. Inquiries into the allegations of scientific misconduct were not concluded but only at a very early stage, partly due to limited capacity. Two issues were identified for closer examination: first, the charge that Homolka's PhD thesis at King's College London may be excessively dependent on an unpublished 1986 manuscript by the Freiburg theologian Professor Dorothee Schlenke (entitled "Normativität und Geschichte"), thereby calling into question the extent of its original contribution; and second, the striking pattern that in the prefaces to several sole-authored books, Homolka offers unusually effusive thanks to his partner for assistance, which could raise additional questions about the independence of authorship in some of these publications.

As for the first issue, The Report (2022, p. 14) notes that Homolka completed his PhD at King's College London in 1992 under the title *From Essence to Existence: Leo Baeck and Religious Identity as a Problem of Continuity and Change in Liberal Jewish and Protestant Theology*. In the preface to the 1994 German version of this work (*Jüdische Identität in der modernen Welt*:

Leo Baeck und der deutsche Protestantismus), he explicitly states that he was able to rely “substantially” on the findings of Schlenke concerning the relationship between liberal theology and Judaism around 1900. The commission therefore considers it necessary to determine whether the doubts about the dissertation’s originality are substantiated (translational or near-verbatim plagiarism), or whether Homolka’s remark should instead be interpreted as a legitimate acknowledgment of an important source of inspiration, but which was otherwise not citable. It is extremely difficult for me to understand how the Commission could even entertain the possibility that an unpublished work is not citable. Why would that be, given the fact that unpublished materials are routinely cited in academic, legal, and administrative contexts and that citability depends on provenance, not publication status?

As for the second issue, expressions of gratitude to his partner in the prefaces of his book could be read as suggesting that substantial parts of the respective books were in fact written not by Homolka but by his partner (ghost writing). According to one of Homolka’s colleagues, this suspicion applies in particular to the 2009 volume *Das jüdische Eherecht*. It is intended, The Report (2022, p. 14) explains, to investigate these claims if more concrete indications emerge and additional information from this colleague has been requested. At the same time, The Report (2022, p. 14) emphasizes that it is standard academic practice to thank colleagues, friends, staff, student assistants, librarians, translators, and others for intellectual, bibliographical, or technical support in prefaces or postscripts, and that such acknowledgements do not in themselves constitute evidence of improper authorship. This constitutes a fair assessment when considered against the evidence referenced.

At the hearing with Homolka and his partner on 22 July 2022, no new substantive evidence emerged on either issue, according to The Report. Homolka portrayed his reference to Schlenke in the German edition of his dissertation as a transparent acknowledgment of a source that could not be cited in the usual way. The partner described his contribution to certain publications as purely editorial rather than intellectual, emphasizing that Homolka consistently pursued his own authorial objectives and neither sought nor accepted substantive input. The investigating committee therefore recommended that the allegation of scientific misconduct be referred to the university’s standing Committee for the Investigation of Scientific Misconduct for further examination.

So much, then, for The Report (2022) with respect to the two allegations of academic misconduct recorded by the University of Potsdam. In its final decision of 12 September 2025 on my appeal against an earlier refusal of a freedom-of-information request, the University of Potsdam confirmed that, in 2023, it had conducted a preliminary review to determine whether a formal procedure should be opened under § 12 of its Statute on the Safeguarding of Good Scientific Practice to investigate allegations of scientific misconduct. This review, carried out by the then dean of the Faculty of Arts, examined publications by Homolka beyond his dissertation. In accordance with the statute, the preliminary procedure was closed after no sufficient grounds for suspecting scientific misconduct were found in the works published during Homolka’s tenure as a full professor at the University of Potsdam (see Fehige 2025d, p. 2)

The University of Potsdam also confirmed that Homolka’s PhD dissertation had been subject of a separate review by King’s College London, the institution that awarded the degree, since only

the degree-granting university is authorized to revoke an academic degree. King's College London had just recently communicated the outcome of its review, the university advised, and it was currently being examined in order to decide on any further steps (see Fehige 2025d, p. 2).

On 16 February 2023, the *Frankfurter Allgemeine Zeitung* (FAZ), one of Germany's leading national newspapers, published an article that substantiated the plausibility of the plagiarism allegations by reporting that more than sixty pages of Homolka's 1992 King's College London dissertation closely parallel Schlenke's unpublished 1986 typescript (see Schmoll 2023). Drawing on a detailed comparison of both documents, the article notes that extensive passages display nearly identical wording and argumentative structure.

The contested sections comprise chapters 3–6 of Homolka's PhD thesis, according to the *FAZ* article. Homolka reproduced Schlenke's arguments almost wholesale, the article argues, adding only superficial linking sentences (translational plagiarism). Examples are cited in the article to illustrate the extent of the overlap (see Fehige 2025j). In a broadcast interview on 30 October 2023 with *Deutschlandfunk*, a major public radio station, Professor Manfred Görtemaker confirmed the thrust of these findings. Having examined both texts himself, he characterized the relationship between them as “a plagiarism of the purest kind” (“Ein Plagiat reinsten Wassers”).

The *FAZ* article further points out that the digital version of Homolka's dissertation—previously available through King's College London's online thesis library—has disappeared from the catalogue soon after the *FAZ* had reached out to Homolka to ask for clarification, and that the university has offered no public explanation for its removal. King's College London disclosed on 7 May 2025 that it is “withholding its release due to the author's request for the digital thesis to be taken down.” (see Fehige 2025b.)

There is a third issue, raised in an undated anonymous report (hereafter: Anonymous Report 2025). The report argues that the alleged plagiarism in the King's College London dissertation is not an isolated case but indicative of a recurring pattern of problematic scholarly practices, including heavy reliance on secondary literature presented as if it reflected direct engagement with Hebrew legal sources, misleading citation of primary texts, and the republication or translation of existing textbook material under Homolka's sole or joint authorship without clear attribution to the original author. If substantiated, the alleged practices correspond to three recognised forms of academic misconduct: (1) disguised source plagiarism, where secondary literature is presented as primary research; (2) misleading or misattributed citation, a form of citation plagiarism; and (3) unacknowledged textual reuse, including translation plagiarism, where existing textbook material is reproduced without attribution. The University of Potsdam disclosed that it plans to review another publication from the period before Homolka's appointment as a full professor, dating from a time when he was already affiliated with the university (see Fehige 2025d, p. 2). I take this to indicate that the University has, at least in principle, also registered this third set of concerns.

In summary, the allegations concerning Homolka centre on three issues. First, it is alleged that substantial portions of his PhD thesis may derive from an unpublished 1986 typescript authored by someone else (translation plagiarism). Second, several of his sole-authored books are alleged to have involved undisclosed assistance by someone else (ghost writing). These allegations were

brought to the University of Potsdam in 2022 and subsequently entered the public domain through reporting on the university's investigative procedures. The plagiarism allegation regarding the dissertation has also been examined independently by a senior journalist of a major newspaper and by a senior university professor familiar with the relevant texts, both of whom publicly stated that they identified extensive textual parallels (see Fehige 2025j). Homolka participated in a hearing before the University of Potsdam's investigative commission. With respect to public scrutiny, access to the digital version of his PhD thesis has been restricted at his own request, as confirmed by King's College (see Fehige (2025b)). A third issue concerns allegations of a recurring pattern of problematic scholarly practices (disguised source plagiarism; citation plagiarism; translation plagiarism) in at least three further publications by Homolka—an issue that appears to have been recognized by the University of Potsdam (see Fehige 2025d).

(2) The Investigative Process

The reconstruction offered in this section is based on documents and correspondence available at the time of writing. Some of my appeals and complaints are still pending, and nothing in this account is intended to gain leverage in those ongoing proceedings; its sole purpose is to analyse the institutional handling of the case, and to facilitate further scholarly discussion of the policy implications of this case.

At the beginning of 2025, I commenced work on my current research project, which examines the transformation of confessional theology at public universities in reunified Germany. A key aspect of this transformation is the shift from a formerly homogeneous Christian framework to a more pluralist landscape, including the establishment of departments of Islamic and Jewish theology. When I turned to the case of the “School of Jewish Theology,” it quickly became apparent that the various investigations into allegations of academic misconduct involving Homolka had not yet led to a publicly transparent resolution. This prompted me to inquire further into the reasons for this ongoing lack of clarity in this important matter.

I decided to contact King's College London first. On 20 January 2025, I wrote to the Research Integrity Office to ask whether the College had received a formal request to investigate the allegations concerning Homolka's PhD thesis, and, if so, whether an investigation had been conducted, whether it had been concluded, and whether any resulting report had been made publicly available. Two days later, I received a courteously phrased response. But it did not address the procedural questions I had raised and did not comply with the disclosure obligations established under the UK Freedom of Information Act (FOIA hereafter).

On January 23, 2025, I submitted another FOIA request, therefore; this time to the compliance department at King's, and I included the request to have access to a digital copy of Homolka's dissertation. My intention here was to assess the plagiarism allegations concerning the 1992 PhD thesis myself and I was hoping King's would send me a digital copy of the text of the dissertation so that I was able to do that. I received a response on February 20, 2025 (see Fehige 2025a). The university confirmed that it held the relevant information but declined disclosure on two grounds.

First, with respect to my request for a digital copy of the dissertation, King’s College London invoked two exemptions under FOIA. Relying on Section 40(2) (personal data), the College argued that disclosure would be unfair because Homolka had requested the digital version of his thesis be taken down and it would not fall within his “reasonable expectations” for the work to be distributed electronically. King’s referred to its internal take-down policy in support of its decision to honour the author’s request. Notably, King’s did not offer access to a scan of a physical copy of the dissertation that its library may hold. This is likely because the College additionally relied on Section 43(2) FOIA (commercial interests), contending that disclosure could prejudice Homolka’s financial interests, given that a commercially available book version of the thesis exists. On this basis, the College withheld the dissertation.

Second, with respect to my request for information on whether King’s had conducted an investigation into the plagiarism allegations, the university relied on Section 40(5A)–(5B) FOIA, stating that it could neither confirm nor deny the existence of any relevant records. To do so, it argued, would in itself amount to a disclosure of personal data contrary to the United Kingdom General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR hereafter). The letter concluded by setting out my appeal rights, including the option to request an internal review (appeal) and, if still dissatisfied, to escalate the matter to the UK Information Commissioner’s Office (ICO hereafter).

On 23 February 2025, I lodged an appeal, and on 7 May 2025 King’s College London issued its decision, upholding its original response to my FOIA request with minor modifications (see Fehige 2025b). I subsequently submitted a complaint about this decision to the ICO, on the grounds that King’s had exceeded the statutory time limit for responding and, in my view, had misapplied FOIA and GDPR, and a decision is still pending (see Fehige 2025f). As of the time of writing, attempts to obtain clarity from King’s have therefore led to no substantive progress. Based on the reasoning provided in its correspondence, it appears to be the position of King’s that UK data protection prevent the university from providing public accountability with respect to the plagiarism allegations concerning Homolka’s 1992 PhD thesis, and that freedom-of-information law gives the public no right to seek clarity, transparency, and accountability. I note that this lack of progress occurred three years after the plagiarism allegations were first made public. An unresolved delay of this length, in the absence of clear justification, should be regarded on ethical grounds as a significant procedural deficiency—measured by the ethical implications of plagiarism allegations that I previously outlined.

Meanwhile, I also sought clarification from the University of Potsdam regarding the steps it had taken to address the allegations of academic misconduct against Homolka. On 24 April 2025, I submitted a freedom-of-information request under German law to the Office of the President of the University of Potsdam. The University’s initial decision of 6 June 2025 denied my request (see Fehige 2025c). I lodged an appeal the same day, and on 12 September 2025 received the corresponding decision (see Fehige 2025d), in which the University annulled its earlier refusal and confirmed the following points in response to my original request of 24 April 2025: (1) the University had formally asked King’s College London to investigate the allegations concerning Homolka’s 1992 PhD thesis; King’s had not responded for an extended period, but a report has now been received and is currently under review by the University; (2) preliminary proceedings under the University’s plagiarism policy were conducted in 2023, but these did not yield findings that substantiated the allegations; and (3) the University plans to initiate new proceedings

extending the scope of review to publications produced before Homolka’s appointment as a full professor, during a period in which he was already affiliated with the institution.

In a subsequent freedom-of-information request to the University of Potsdam, I asked to see the report received from King’s College London, the report that concluded the plagiarism proceedings in 2023, and any documents underlying the University’s decision to initiate new plagiarism proceedings. On 30 October 2025, this request was denied (see Fehige 2025e), and on the following day I lodged an appeal, which is currently pending.

In response to an inquiry from the press regarding the status of a report from King’s College London about the plagiarism allegations concerning Homolka’s 1992 thesis, the University of Potsdam’s press office stated on 13 November 2025 that the University had “still not received a final report from King’s College London,” adding that in August it had been informed that the procedure was nearing completion, but that no further information had been received since then (see Fehige 2025h; my translation; see also Fehige 2025i). This statement is difficult to reconcile with the information that the University of Potsdam disclosed before (see Fehige 2025d). The following synopsis presents the relevant statements verbatim (with my English translations).

University of Potsdam in September of 2025 (see Fehige 2025d)	University of Potsdam’s Press Office Statement in November of 2025 (see Fehige 2025h; see also Fehige 2025i)
<p>“Das King’s College London hat mittlerweile das Ergebnis der dortigen Überprüfung mitgeteilt. Dieses wird zurzeit ausgewertet, um auf dieser Grundlage über das weitere Vorgehen zu befinden.“</p>	<p>“Der UP liegt leider immer noch kein Abschlussbericht des King’s College London vor. Der UP wurde im August mitgeteilt, dass der Abschluss des Verfahrens bevorsteht. Seitdem haben uns keine weiteren Informationen vom KCL erreicht.“</p>
<p>My translation:</p> <p>King’s College London has now communicated the outcome of its review. This outcome is currently being evaluated in order to determine the next steps.</p>	<p>My translation:</p> <p>Unfortunately, the University of Potsdam has still not received a final report from King’s College London. In August we were informed that the conclusion of the procedure was imminent. Since then, we have not received any further information from KCL.</p>

As of the time of writing, it remains unclear how the University of Potsdam’s two contradictory disclosures can be reconciled.

It is important to stress that Homolka denies all plagiarism allegations. In a letter to the editor of a journal that had accepted one of my articles on the Homolka affair, he states that a committee at King’s College had investigated the plagiarism allegations and that, according to him, “the committee found no grounds for academic misconduct” (Fehige 2025g, p. 3). It is impossible for the public to verify the truth of the claim.

In summary, efforts to obtain clarity about the status and progress of the investigations conducted by King’s College London and the University of Potsdam—more than three years after the

allegations of academic misconduct became known to both universities and to the public—have been rather unsuccessful. The available evidence points to a landscape characterized by pronounced procedural opacity, extended delays, and conflicting institutional communications. King’s has consistently declined to confirm even the existence of an inquiry into the plagiarism allegations, while simultaneously restricting access to Homolka’s dissertation at his request. The University of Potsdam, by contrast, has confirmed that it requested an investigation from King’s, conducted a preliminary review in 2023, and intends to broaden the scope of inquiry to additional publications; yet it has also denied access to relevant documents and, at one point, issued a public statement (there is no report from King’s) that conflicts with information contained in a previous formal appeal decision (there is a report from King’s). These interactions, taken together, make it difficult to reconstruct the status of the investigations or to understand the procedural steps that have been taken, and they underscore the challenges that arise when key academic institutions do not—or cannot—provide transparent and timely accounts of their handling of allegations of academic misconduct.

(3) It’s not about the odd bad apple

This part of the paper is structured around a single pressing question: whether a duration of more than three years is acceptable, within a public system of knowledge, for resolving the kind of academic-misconduct allegations at issue here. I will argue that it is not, offer several reasons in support of this claim, and formulate concrete policy recommendations.

First, Broad and Wade’s (1985) analysis rejects the notion that scientific fraud is merely the work of a few “bad apples.” Instead, they argue that misconduct is symptomatic of structural weaknesses inherent in every system of public knowledge—weaknesses that require key actors, such as universities, to respond promptly and carefully when plagiarism allegations arise. “The ‘bad apples’ who commit fraud,” Broad and Wade (1985, 78) argue, “are a special fruit of the system.” They define plagiarism as “the wholesale theft of another’s work” and note that it is “so outrageous and obvious a crime that an outsider might predict” no scientist would commit it; “the evidence shows that, to the contrary, plagiarism in science is not rare,” that it “probably often escapes detection,” and that “even the most blatant cases” can take considerable time to prove, according to Broad and Wade (1985, 59). If this diagnosis is sound, then in the absence of any public account for such a delay, it is difficult to regard the time it took King’s College London to transmit a report to the University of Potsdam (assuming it is true that it did) as unacceptable within a system that claims to uphold academic integrity.

While the legal issues raised by King’s conduct are currently before the ICO, the lack of any explanation for the delay—combined with the College’s refusal to provide even minimal public accountability on the basis of its interpretation of the relevant UK legal frameworks—raises substantial ethical concerns. At a minimum, this is unfair to the University of Potsdam, assuming that it has an interest in bringing the matter to a resolution. It is also unfair to the scholar whose work is alleged to have been plagiarized—Schlenke. Finally, the broader institutional context matters: Jewish theology in Germany is far from securely established. The “School of Jewish Theology” is a highly unusual institution within Germany’s system of public knowledge, and its success or failure may have significant implications for the future of Jewish theology in the

country, not least because the history of the School has been tightly intertwined with Homolka's person.

The allegations of scientific misconduct emerged alongside other serious accusations and, taken together, may indicate larger structural problems involving several key stakeholders in the School's future, including the administration of the University of Potsdam, the Central Council of Jews in Germany, and leaders of the Jewish communities who sponsor the rabbinical and cantorial seminaries that the School is intended to serve (see Moser 2023). At present, only two tenured professors remain at the School, one of them being Homolka. If the allegations of plagiarism were to be substantiated, questions could arise as to whether he can reasonably remain in his post, given that his appointment was based in part on the PhD from King's College—at least, this is the view expressed by Görtemaker (2023). In that scenario, the School would be left with a single tenured appointment, and in light of the developments of the past three years, this could have implications for the future of Jewish theology as a confessional theology department at the University of Potsdam, particularly in relation to the existing, comparatively strong Jewish Studies program. It is also relevant that the rabbinical and cantorial seminaries were already producing rabbis and cantors before the School was established—with the support of the Jewish Studies program.

It is unnecessary to exaggerate the significance of the Homolka case. At the same time, it would be equally misguided to treat it as an isolated “bad apple” scenario. Broad and Wade (1985, 52, 285) summarize the lessons of the Elias Abdel Kuder Alsabti case (1954–1990)—an Iraqi would-be cancer researcher who built an academic career on forged credentials and plagiarized papers, mostly in cancer immunology—in stark terms. They note that:

“Alsabti, in the course of constructing his academic illusions, had forged a medical degree, had duped the Jordanian government into giving him tens of thousands of dollars, had fabricated his relation to the royal family, had lied his way into U.S. universities, has bestowed a Ph.D. upon himself, and, while allegedly doing research in a handful of prestigious labs, had pirated many, perhaps all, of his sixty published papers.”

These actions are extraordinary enough on their own. Yet the more important point, as Broad and Wade (1985, 52) emphasize, is that such conduct becomes possible only when weaknesses in the surrounding system permit and enable it:

“His tactics deceived the editors of scientific journals around the world. In addition, his lies and legerdemain took in the government of two Middle Eastern countries, the review committees of eleven scientific societies, and the administration from six U.S. institutions of higher education.”

It is in this sense that Alan Posener (2022) speaks of a “Homolka system,” a characterization that raises broader concerns about the ethical culture surrounding the School of Jewish Theology. As Stricker and Günther (2019, 61) remind us, scientific misconduct cannot be fully prevented by detection mechanisms alone; prevention also requires the cultivation of an ethical organizational culture that communicates clearly which forms of behaviour are acceptable and which are not. The Homolka affair is also in this specific sense not merely about the actions of a single individual. Ultimately, the publicly unexplained delay in investigating the plagiarism allegations

risks creating the impression that King’s College London may be acting in a manner that appears to protect its own institutional interests—or even Homolka’s—simply because the total absence of transparency leaves space for such interpretations.

In this context, the persistent lack of clarity regarding the work and membership of the *Ständige Studienkommission für das jüdisch-geistliche Amt* (hereafter: Curricular Commission) is particularly significant. Like all academic units at German universities, confessional theological units are publicly funded and fully embedded within the university, offering research and degree programs (including BA, MA, and PhD/ThD) that are administratively fully integrated into an otherwise secularized university system. Unlike other units, however, non-academic bodies external to the university—namely, state-recognized religious communities—are granted extensive participatory rights in curriculum design and faculty appointments. These arrangements reflect Germany’s distinctive model of positive religious neutrality (or worldview neutrality) and its cooperative relationship between the state and state-recognized religious communities.

At the School, the Curricular Commission was intended to embody this cooperation in exemplary ways, based on an agreement dated 5 July 2013 between the University of Potsdam and the *Union Progressiver Juden in Deutschland e.V.*—which presents itself as representing the liberal/reform tradition of Judaism in Germany—and *Masorti e.V. Deutschland*—which presents itself as representing the conservative tradition of Judaism. The agreement “regulates the participatory and objection rights of the” Curricular Commission in curricular and personnel matters (Gercke Wollschläger Report 2023, p. 79). In principle, a well-functioning Curricular Commission could have provided an important counterbalance to the dynamics that Posener describes as the “Homolka system.” Yet, as The Report (2022, p. 11; my translation) notes, “The role of the [Curricular Commission]—a commission responsible for exercising the rights of participation under Germany’s constitutional law on religion in the establishment of confessional degree programs and in personnel decisions—could not be conclusively clarified.” This unresolved lack of clarity warrants careful attention and, arguably, decisive corrective action for the sake of an ethical culture at the School in the sense specified.

I come to my second argument. It was initially appropriate for the University of Potsdam to defer to King’s College with respect to the assessment of Homolka’s PhD thesis. However, once King’s College failed to provide timely updates on the status or progress of its inquiry (see Fehige 2025d), the University of Potsdam’s continued inaction becomes not open to question by established ethical standards, but even under the university’s own plagiarism policy.

Relevant in this respect is § 9 section 2 of that policy, and I am grateful to Professor Manfred Görtemaker for drawing my attention to that section of the policy. It reads, in my translation, as follows:

“The procedure for clarifying scientific misconduct shall also create the possibility of resolving arising conflict cases on a purely professional (i.e., academic) level in a manner that appropriately takes into account the interests involved. All parties involved shall be given the opportunity to develop solutions on this professional level.”

§ 9(2) imposes a rule that requires the administration to provide a functioning mechanism for resolution. It mandates a process that enables solutions which appropriately consider the interests of all parties involved on the level of professional (academic) assessment. A multi-year absence of progress is the opposite of enabling such a process. If the administration does not take steps to ensure this—by waiting passively for an external institution for several years—then it is difficult to see how it could be fulfilling the mandate of § 9(2) of its own plagiarism policy.

The “professional” or “academic” level referenced in § 9(2) presupposes an actual academic evaluation of the allegations. When the university defers for years to a foreign institution that does not respond to inquiries, does not provide timelines, and does not produce any formal outcome (see Fehige 2025d), then no professional or academically grounded solution is possible. Yet enabling such a solution is precisely what § 9(2) obliges the university to do.

Nothing in § 9—which concerns the internal safeguarding of academic integrity—requires, or even contemplates, that the university may outsource this responsibility indefinitely to an external institution. The opposite is suggested. The purpose of § 9 is the internal safeguarding of academic integrity; the mechanisms described in §§ 11–12 presuppose timely action; and § 9(2) explicitly states that the process must provide all parties with a meaningful opportunity to reach a solution that appropriately considers their interests on the level of professional academic assessment.

I come to my third and final argument. Given that some of the evidence supporting the allegations is public, the University of Potsdam should have explained to the public the reasons for the prolonged delay in reaching a resolution and, in addition, made public the report of the proceedings it states were undertaken in 2023, which I assume were conducted in accordance with § 11 of its plagiarism policy. To date, however, no such report has been published, and even my application for access to it has, thus far, been unsuccessful. This stands in stark contrast to basic requirements of transparency and accountability, and is particularly troubling given the systemic nature of research misconduct.

The inaccessibility of the report even upon freedom of information request adds gravity to the situation in this particular case, as the University of Potsdam appears to apply the same freedom-of-information rules in inconsistent ways. It acknowledged a public right of access to information in the Homolka case in September of 2025 (see Fehige 2025d), whereas roughly a month later, it denies that right (see Fehige 2025e). There also appears to be a discrepancy regarding the existence of a final report from King’s College. In September, the University affirms that such a report exists (see Fehige 2025d), and in November of 2025 the press office has states that no final report is available (see Fehige 2025h and 2025i). A clear commitment to accountability, transparency, and academic integrity would, one might reasonably conclude, look very different from what we have seen from the University of Potsdam.

In the context of the kind of institutional analysis I mean to offer here, it extremely important not ascribe intentions and motivations to individual actors and decision makers. Against the backdrop of Michel Foucault’s notion of “regulative power”, the shortcomings that I have identified on the part of King’s College and the University of Potsdam are better understood as effects of institutional structures and incentives rather than as outcomes of the personal motives

or intentions of individual actors. Following Wolfgang Detel (2005, 11-47), I define Foucault's "regulative power" as follows: an agent P_1 has regulative power over an agent P_2 when P_1 has both the opportunity and the means to bring about circumstances U such that, given P_2 's own intentions and beliefs, it is rational for P_2 to do X ; when P_1 intentionally brings about such circumstances in pursuit of ends Z for which P_2 's doing X is necessary; and when P_2 in fact occasionally does X on the basis of the circumstances U that P_1 has created. P_1 and P_2 are normally distinct, and the existence of regulative power in this sense does not imply reciprocity. In the absence of a clear awareness of regulative power, there is a persistent risk of explaining developments in the institutional response to the plagiarism allegations against Homolka by ascribing specific intentions or motives to individual actors.

This is the interpretive strategy of Homolka (2022): he contends that those who have raised or advanced the allegations are acting out of malicious intent and seek his removal, and he explains this alleged intent in terms of what he presents as the Central Council of Jews in Germany's broader agenda for the Jewish community—an agenda that, in his view, encounters effective and unwelcome resistance in him as a prominent advocate of non-orthodox forms of Jewish life in Germany (see also Fehige 2025g). Such an approach surely obscures the pivotal ways in which the actions of the various parties reflect a convergence—and at times a conflict—of institutional interests rather than coordinated personal strategies.

The central insight of regulative power is that influence is exercised not primarily by coercing individuals and conscious cooperation among decision makers, but by structuring the circumstances under which it becomes rational, advantageous, or low-cost for others to act in particular ways. In this sense, the concept could help to illuminate, beyond what is attempted in this paper, the institutional dynamics at play in the development of the School of Jewish Theology and the subsequent institutional inability to respond to the allegations under consideration in a timely and transparent manner—regardless of whether any specific allegation is true. An institution such as the University of Potsdam may have strong incentives to protect the visibility and stability of a newly established programme like the School of Jewish Theology—which even required amendments to the constitution of the *Land* Brandenburg prior to its establishment—and may thereby unintentionally create circumstances in which delaying the assessment of allegations, minimising reputational risk, or communicating cautiously with external bodies becomes a rational course of action for multiple actors. The ends Z (stabilising the institution, preserving alliances, avoiding political exposure) can make certain responses appear rational, even if they risk undermining the academic integrity of both the University of Potsdam more broadly and the School in particular.

Taken together, the three strands of analysis developed in this section—the systemic account of scientific fraud, the obligations imposed by the University of Potsdam's own plagiarism policy, and the documented inconsistencies in both institutions' handling of transparency and freedom-of-information procedures—point toward three policy recommendations for universities operating within public systems of knowledge.

1. *Establish time-bound and publicly accountable timelines for serious academic-misconduct inquiries.* The first argument shows that misconduct is not an aberration attributable to isolated individuals but a structural feature of knowledge systems. If misconduct is systemic, then long,

unexplained periods of institutional inactivity undermine the very mechanisms meant to counteract it. Universities should therefore adopt explicit maximum timeframes for key stages of serious misconduct proceedings—particularly for allegations concerning already-awarded degrees or senior academic appointments. Cases that exceed these timeframes should trigger a duty to issue a reasoned public explanation, accompanied by a revised timeline and a statement identifying which parts of the process are delayed and why. In cross-institutional cases, universities should agree on formal protocols that define reporting duties, shared responsibilities, and communication expectations. Absent such mechanisms, the prolonged opacity documented in this case study—three years without clear institutional action or explanation—becomes indistinguishable from institutional inaction.

2. Require institutions to maintain internal responsibility for academic-integrity processes, even when external bodies possess formal jurisdiction. The second argument indicates that externalizing responsibility for a multi-year period is incompatible with the University of Potsdam’s internal duties under its plagiarism policy. The relevant policy explicitly requires the university to create a process that enables “professional”—that is, academically grounded—resolution that takes account of all parties’ interests. Universities should therefore treat external investigations not as substitutes for their own obligations but as inputs into them. When an external institution (such as the degree-granting university) fails to communicate progress, as occurred in the case under consideration, universities should initiate their own investigations, trigger independent expert reviews, or otherwise activate internal mechanisms rather than remain in a posture of indefinite deferral. A strict norm of non-outsourcing of responsibility—especially where internal policy mandates timely academic resolution—would help prevent situations in which deferral becomes indistinguishable from abdication.

3. Strengthen transparency obligations and harmonize freedom-of-information practices to prevent procedural opacity in high-stakes cases. The third argument has identified systematic inconsistencies in both universities’ communication practices, including conflicting statements regarding even the existence of a report, inconsistent application of FOI rules, and the absence of any public explanation for the prolonged delay. These contradictions undermine institutional credibility, erode public trust, and—particularly in structurally fragile fields such as the School of Jewish Theology—risk damaging the legitimacy of the discipline itself. Universities should adopt policies requiring (a) minimum mandatory transparency in serious misconduct cases (for example, confirmation that an investigation is underway; periodic statements on its procedural stage; a brief post-conclusion statement); (b) stable and consistent FOI practices, so that the same request cannot generate contradictory outcomes within the same institution; (c) public access to non-personal procedural documents, such as final reports or summaries, with personal data redacted when necessary; and (d) archival stability, meaning that documents necessary for academic scrutiny (for example, dissertations) cannot be removed without a transparent, reviewable justification.

In summary, the analysis of this section suggests that the delays, inconsistencies, and opacity observed in the handling of the allegations are best understood not as the result of the intentions or motives of any individual actor, but as the product of institutional structures and incentives that shape the rational courses of action available to them. Drawing on the notion of regulative power, this perspective shows how universities may, often unintentionally, create circumstances

in which withholding information, deferring decisions, or relying on external bodies appears advantageous, low-cost, or least disruptive—particularly in a structurally fragile field such as Jewish theology. These dynamics do not require coordinated strategies or deliberate obstruction; rather, they arise from the convergence of institutional interests, legal constraints, reputational concerns, and the absence of mechanisms designed to ensure timely and transparent resolution. It is precisely this structural constellation that renders the prolonged procedural uncertainty ethically troubling and institutionally consequential, regardless of whether any specific allegation is ultimately substantiated. The case under consideration should therefore be taken as a strong impetus to revise existing plagiarism and research-integrity policies so that they contain clearer timelines, communication duties, and safeguards against the kinds of prolonged ambiguity documented here.

Conclusion

This paper has discussed the handling of plagiarism allegations against Rabbi Professor Homolka, PhD, PhD, by King's College London and the University of Potsdam as a case study in the vulnerabilities of contemporary systems of public knowledge at the level of university administrations. My aim has not been to adjudicate the truth of the allegations themselves, but to analyse how two major universities—each enjoying a mandate in the generation, certification and circulation of knowledge—have responded to a challenge that touches directly on their responsibility to uphold minimal standards of transparency, accountability, and integrity in an academic matter. In line with Broad and Wade's (1986, 2015) observation that cases of alleged scientific fraud illuminate the non-rational, institutional dimensions of science, I have treated the Homolka affair as a window into the dynamics of regulative power in relation to specific structural and procedural conditions under which academic integrity is either safeguarded or placed at risk.

Three points have emerged. First, the extended delay and lack of publicly accessible information about the status and outcome of King's internal proceedings—combined with the removal of the digital dissertation at the author's request and the restrictive interpretation of freedom of information and data-protection law—create a landscape of opacity that is difficult to reconcile with the role of a university as a guardian of public knowledge. Second, the University of Potsdam's prolonged reliance on an external review, its apparent reluctance to activate its own procedures with the necessary resolve, and the inconsistencies in its freedom-of-information decisions and public statements raise questions about whether its internal mechanisms for addressing allegations of academic misconduct—mechanisms it has itself codified in its plagiarism policy—have been adequately employed. Third, in a field as institutionally fragile as Jewish theology in Germany, where the legitimacy of confessional theology within the university system is contested, such opacity carries particular risks for the perceived credibility of the discipline as a whole. In other words, in a field whose academic legitimacy is contested, prolonged opacity in addressing serious allegations risks not only weakening confidence in the individuals involved but also jeopardizing the broader project of establishing Jewish Theology as a credible and durable academic discipline in the German public university system.

The analysis presented here indicates that effective governance of academic integrity requires clearer timelines, stronger internal responsibilities, and more consistent transparency practices.

Universities should adopt explicit, publicly reviewable timeframes for serious misconduct proceedings; ensure that internal academic-integrity mechanisms remain active even when external bodies hold formal jurisdiction; and implement harmonized communication and freedom-of-information standards that prevent contradictory or opaque institutional responses. These measures are particularly important in structurally fragile academic fields, where prolonged uncertainty and inconsistent communication can undermine not only confidence in individual cases but also the credibility of the discipline as a whole. Collectively, such reforms would reduce the institutional vulnerabilities revealed by this case and strengthen the integrity of public systems of knowledge.

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